
Kingfisher is making new friends in Indonesia

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Thanks to the translation by Prof. Ni Putu Wulan Purnama Sari, Mr. Kingfisher has had the opportunity to travel to Indonesia, immerse himself in the country's rich culture, and make new friends.

Although the translation is still under production, it has already received a warm welcome from Indonesian readers. Among them, Dr. Inge Wattimena Benjamin kindly offered an insightful evaluation of Mr. Kingfisher:

“The author portrays Kingfisher as a bird whose strengths can be applied to human life. Kingfisher uses his senses and experiences, cultivating knowledge and skills to survive. He is intelligent and meticulous in planning and calculating his actions, never gives up when facing challenges or threats, and actively seeks solutions that bring him happiness. Kingfisher holds his dignity in high regard. The author skillfully and thoughtfully packages Kingfisher's life in a simple story that is easy for readers to understand. The translator arranged the translated text neatly and effectively, successfully conveying the author's intended meaning to Indonesian readers.”

The image of Mr. Kingfisher has resonated greatly with Dr. Benjamin, who is also a bird lover. Sharing the same affection for birds, she composed a poem titled “Mother Bird and Sparrow” to express her love:

*“Once upon a time in a bird’s nest
mother bird and sparrow
spread their charm together*

*patiently sharing
mutually respecting
listening to news
about the bustling noise of the world*

*in harmony and peace while united
until the time comes to bid farewell
leaving the nest to work independently
upon the vast divine expanse beyond.”*

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Hopefully, once the book is officially published, Mr. Kingfisher will continue to gain new friends in Indonesia and further inspire hearts across cultures.

References

[1] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://books.google.com/books?id=N10jEQAAQBAJ>

[2] Benjamin IW. (2025). Induk Dan Emprit. <https://lupuis.com/painting/induk-dan-emprit/>

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